

Thinking about the communication dashboards, how likely are you to use the following information for your project. Please briefly explain.

- Community network

By gender

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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by affiliation

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Pull requests that need attention and their details

1 - Not very likely	2 - Not Likely	3 - Neutral	4 - Likely	5 - Very likely
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- Is there any other way you would use the communication dashboards that we did not cover? Is there any other information you would like to see in these dashboards?

